

7th Brazilian Symposium on Programming Languages

J.UCS Special Issue

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The Brazilian Symposium on Programming Languages (SBLP) is the main event in South America devoted to programming languages. Its scope includes all aspects of programming languages, including language design and implementation, formal semantics, domain-specific languages, and theoretical foundations of programming languages. The Symposium is a yearly event supported by the Brazilian Computer Society (SBC).

Its 7th edition was held in the town of Ouro Preto (declared by UNESCO a Cultural Heritage of Mankind), in the southeast of Brazil, from May 28 to May 30. This year, SBLP attracted 50 submissions. From this total, we got 36 submissions from Brazil, 10 from Europe, three from the US, and one from Uruguay. The program committee selected 16 papers, which we present in this special issue.

Brazil, August 2003

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